

Ion Batteries

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ABSTRACT

Development of Lithium and Sodium ion batteries is essential for portable electronics and electrically powered transportation. An important aspect of the batteries performance is control of the lithium and sodium ion intercalation into the electrode materials. In this project you will look at this process and how it limits performance and how it can improved. One aspect will be looking into ways of getting detailed information on the nanoscale processes by imaging and spectroscopy.